

EXTENDED DATA

Title: Multivariable prediction models for long-term outcomes after hip fracture: a protocol for a systematic review

Authors:

Mary E. Walsh¹
Pia Kjær Kristensen²
Thomas J Hjelholt³
Conor Hurson⁴
Cathal Walsh⁵
Catherine Blake⁶

Author affiliations:

¹School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science, University College Dublin, Dublin 4, Ireland; <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-8920-7419>

²The Department of Clinical Medicine, Orthopaedic, Aarhus University, Denmark; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5473-9386>

³Department of Clinical Epidemiology, Aarhus University Hospital, Denmark; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0112-5801>

⁴Department of Trauma and Orthopaedics, St Vincent's University Hospital, Dublin, Dublin 4, Ireland; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1066-5260>

⁵Department of Mathematics and Statistics, University of Limerick; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6599-9562>

⁶School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science, University College Dublin, Dublin 4, Ireland; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0600-629X>

Corresponding author:

Dr Mary Walsh
School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science,
University College Dublin,
Dublin 4,
Ireland
Email: m.walsh@ucd.ie

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Full Search Strategy

Sources: MEDLINE (Ovid), Embase, Web of Science, CINAHL, Scopus

MEDLINE (Ovid)

Resources: Ovid MEDLINE(R) Epub Ahead of Print and Ovid MEDLINE(R) 1946 to current

1. exp Femoral Fractures/
2. ((hip or hips or cervical or femoral\$ or femur\$ or intracapsular or "intra capsular" or subcapital or "sub capital" or transcervical or "trans cervical" or basicervical or "basi cervical" or extracapsular or "extra capsular" or trochant\$ or subtrochant\$ or pertrochant\$ or intertrochant\$) adj5 (fracture\$ or break\$ or broke\$)).ti,ab,kf.
3. (((head or neck or proximal) adj5 (fracture\$ or break\$ or broke\$)) and (femoral\$ or femur\$)).ti,ab,kf.
4. or/1-3
5. ("clinical prediction" OR "clinical score\$" OR "decision rule*" OR "diagnostic accuracy" OR "diagnostic rule\$" OR "diagnostic score\$" OR "diagnostic value" OR "predictive outcome" OR "predictive rule\$" OR "prediction model\$" OR "prognostic model\$" OR "predictive score\$" OR "predictive value" OR "predictive risk\$" OR "prediction outcome\$" OR "prediction rule\$" OR "prediction score\$" OR "prediction value\$" OR "prediction risk\$" OR "risk score\$" OR "risk model" OR "risk adjust\$" OR "risk prediction" OR "validation decision\$" OR "validation rule\$" OR "validation score\$" OR "external validation" OR (derivation AND validation) OR (derived AND validated) OR (sensitivity AND specificity)).ti,ab,kf.
6. ("Stratification" or "Discrimination" or "Discriminate" or "c-statistic" or "c statistic" or "Area under the curve" or "Calibration" or "Indices" or "Algorithm").ti,ab,kf.
7. ROC Curve/
8. or/5-7
9. 4 AND 8
10. "Hip Fracture Score".mp.
11. 9 OR 10.
12. (Mortality or death or died or survival or readmi* or re-admi* or rehospitali* or re-hospitali* or re-operat* or reoperat* or failure or revision or periprosthe* or peri-prosthe* or peri-implant or Osteonecro* or "avascular necro*" or non-union or "non union" or extrusion or cutout or cut-out or re-fracture or refracture or "second fracture" or recurrent or subsequent or dislocation or infect* or complicat* or adverse or event* or reaction or transfusion or thrombo* or embol* or residen* or living or home or location or lived or function* or adhere* or medicat* or persist* or pain* or mobil* or walk* or ambulat* or quality or QOL or activit*).ti,ab,kf.
13. 11 AND 12.

Embase

(Limit to Embase Not MEDLINE)

1. 'femur fracture'/exp OR 'hip fracture'/exp
2. ((hip OR hips OR cervical or femoral* OR femur* or intracapsular or intra-capsular or subcapital or sub-capital or transcervical or trans-cervical or basicervical or basi-cervical or extracapsular or extra-capsular or trochant* or subtrochant* or pertrochant* or intertrochant*) NEAR/5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)):ab,kw,ti
3. (((head OR neck OR proximal) NEAR/5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)):ab,kw,ti) AND (femoral* OR femur*):ab,kw,ti
4. or/1-3
5. ('clinical prediction' OR "clinical score\$" OR "decision rule\$" OR 'diagnostic accuracy' OR "diagnostic rule\$" OR "diagnostic score\$" OR "diagnostic value" OR "predictive outcome\$" OR "predictive rule\$" OR "predictive score\$" OR "predictive value" OR "predictive risk\$" OR "prediction outcome\$" OR "prediction rule\$" OR "prediction score\$" OR "prediction value\$" OR "prediction risk\$" OR "risk score\$" OR 'risk model' OR 'risk adjust*' OR 'risk prediction' OR "validation decision\$" OR "validation rule\$" OR "validation score\$" OR (derivation AND validation):ab,kw,ti OR (derived AND validated) :ab,kw,ti OR (sensitivity AND specificity) :ab,kw,ti
6. ("Stratification" or "Discrimination" or "Discriminate" or "c-statistic" or "c statistic" or "Area under the curve" or "Calibration" or "Indices" or "Algorithm"):ab,kw,ti
7. 'receiver operating characteristic'/de
8. or/5-7
9. 4 AND 8
10. 'hip fracture score'
11. 9 OR 10.
12. (Mortality OR death OR died OR survival OR readmi* OR re-admi* OR rehospitalli* OR re-hospitalli* OR re-operat* OR reoperat* OR failure OR revision OR periprosthe* OR peri-prosthe* OR peri-implant OR osteonecro* OR "avascular necro*" OR non-union OR "non union" OR extrusion OR cutout OR cut-out OR re-fracture OR refracture OR "second fracture" OR recurrent OR subsequent OR dislocation OR infect* OR complicat* OR adverse or event* OR reaction OR transfusion OR thrombo* OR embol* OR residen* OR living OR home OR location OR lived OR function* OR adhere* OR medicat* OR persist* OR pain* OR mobil* OR walk* OR ambulat* OR quality OR QOL OR activit*):ab,kw,ti
13. 11 AND 12.

Web of Science

Editions = SCI-EXPANDED

1 (((TI=(((hip or hips or cervical or femoral* or femur* or intracapsular or intracapsular or subcapital or subcapital or transcervical or transcervical or basicervical or basicervical or extracapsular or extracapsular or trochant* or subtrochant* or pertrochant* or intertrochant*) NEAR/5(fracture* or break* or broke*)))) OR AB=(((hip or hips or cervical or femoral* or femur* or intracapsular or intracapsular or subcapital or subcapital or transcervical or transcervical or basicervical or basicervical or extracapsular or extracapsular or trochant* or subtrochant* or pertrochant* or intertrochant*) NEAR/5(fracture* or break* or broke*))) OR KP=(((hip or hips or cervical or femoral* or femur* or intracapsular or intracapsular or subcapital or subcapital or transcervical or transcervical or basicervical or basicervical or extracapsular or extracapsular or trochant* or subtrochant* or pertrochant* or intertrochant*) NEAR/5(fracture* or break* or broke*)))

2 ((TI=(((head or neck or proximal) NEAR/5(fracture* or break* or broke*)) and (femoral* or femur*))) OR AB=(((head or neck or proximal) NEAR/5(fracture* or break* or broke*)) and (femoral* or femur*))) OR KP=(((head or neck or proximal) NEAR/5(fracture* or break* or broke*)) and (femoral* or femur*))

3 #2 OR #1

4 ((TI=('clinical prediction' OR "clinical score*" OR "decision rule*" OR 'diagnostic accuracy' OR "diagnostic rule*" OR 'diagnostic score*' OR 'diagnostic value' OR 'predictive outcome*' OR 'predictive rule*' OR 'predictive score*' OR 'predictive value' OR "predictive risk*" OR "prediction outcome*" OR "prediction rule*" OR "prediction score*" OR "prediction value*" OR "prediction risk*" OR "risk score*" OR "risk model" OR "risk adjust*" OR "risk prediction" OR "validation decision*" OR "validation rule*" OR "validation score*" OR (derivation AND validation) OR (derived AND validated) OR (sensitivity AND specificity))) OR AB=('clinical prediction' OR "clinical score*" OR "decision rule*" OR 'diagnostic accuracy' OR "diagnostic rule*" OR 'diagnostic score*' OR 'diagnostic value' OR 'predictive outcome*' OR 'predictive rule*' OR 'predictive score*' OR 'predictive value' OR "predictive risk*" OR "prediction outcome*" OR "prediction rule*" OR "prediction score*" OR "prediction value*" OR "prediction risk*" OR "risk score*" OR "risk model" OR "risk adjust*" OR "risk prediction" OR "validation decision*" OR "validation rule*" OR "validation score*" OR (derivation AND validation) OR (derived AND validated) OR (sensitivity AND specificity))) OR KP=('clinical prediction' OR "clinical score*" OR "decision rule*" OR 'diagnostic accuracy' OR "diagnostic rule*" OR 'diagnostic score*' OR 'diagnostic value' OR 'predictive outcome*' OR 'predictive rule*' OR 'predictive score*' OR 'predictive value' OR "predictive risk*" OR "prediction outcome*" OR "prediction rule*" OR "prediction score*" OR "prediction value*" OR "prediction risk*" OR "risk score*" OR "risk model" OR "risk adjust*" OR "risk prediction" OR "validation decision*" OR "validation rule*" OR "validation score*" OR (derivation AND validation) OR (derived AND validated) OR (sensitivity AND specificity)))

5 (TI=("Stratification" or "Discrimination" or "Discriminate" or "c-statistic" or "c statistic" or "Area under the curve" or "Calibration" or "Indices" or "Algorithm")) OR (AB=("Stratification" or "Discrimination" or "Discriminate" or "c-statistic" or "c statistic" or "Area under the curve" or "Calibration" or "Indices" or "Algorithm")) OR (KP=("Stratification" or "Discrimination" or "Discriminate" or "c-statistic" or "c statistic" or "Area under the curve" or "Calibration" or "Indices" or "Algorithm"))

6 #4 OR #5

7 #3 AND #6

8 TS=("Hip Fracture Score")

9 #8 OR #7

10 ((TI=(Mortality OR death OR died OR survival OR readmi* OR re-admi* OR rehospitali* OR re-hospitali* OR re-operat* OR reoperat* OR failure OR revision OR periprosthe* OR peri-prosthe* OR peri-implant OR osteonecro* OR "avascular necro*" OR non-union OR "non union" OR extrusion OR cutout OR cut-out OR re-fracture OR refracture OR "second fracture" OR recurrent OR subsequent OR dislocation OR infect* OR complicat* OR adverse or event* OR reaction OR transfusion OR thrombo* OR embol* OR residen* OR living OR home OR location OR lived OR function* OR adhere* OR medicat* OR persist* OR pain* OR mobil* OR walk* OR ambulat* OR quality OR QOL OR activit*)) OR AB=(Mortality OR death OR died OR survival OR readmi* OR re-admi* OR rehospitali* OR re-hospitali* OR re-operat* OR reoperat* OR failure OR revision OR periprosthe* OR peri-prosthe* OR peri-implant OR osteonecro* OR "avascular necro*" OR non-union OR "non union" OR extrusion OR cutout OR cut-out OR re-fracture OR refracture OR "second fracture" OR recurrent OR subsequent OR dislocation OR infect* OR complicat* OR adverse or event* OR reaction OR transfusion OR thrombo* OR embol* OR residen* OR living OR home OR location OR lived OR function* OR adhere* OR medicat* OR persist* OR pain* OR mobil* OR walk* OR ambulat* OR quality OR QOL OR activit*)) OR KP=(Mortality OR death OR died OR survival OR readmi* OR re-admi* OR rehospitali* OR re-hospitali* OR re-operat* OR reoperat* OR failure OR revision OR periprosthe* OR peri-prosthe* OR peri-implant OR osteonecro* OR "avascular necro*" OR non-union OR "non union" OR extrusion OR cutout OR cut-out OR re-fracture OR refracture OR "second fracture" OR recurrent OR subsequent OR dislocation OR infect* OR complicat* OR adverse or event* OR reaction OR transfusion OR thrombo* OR embol* OR residen* OR living OR home OR location OR lived OR function* OR adhere* OR medicat* OR persist* OR pain* OR mobil* OR walk* OR ambulat* OR quality OR QOL OR activit*))
#10 AND #9 and Articles (Document Types)

CINAHL (Ebsco)

- S1 (MH "Femoral Fractures+") OR (MH "Hip Fractures+")
- S2 TI ((hip OR hips OR cervical or femoral* OR femur* or intracapsular or intra-capsular or subcapital or sub-capital or transcervical or trans-cervical or basicervical or basi-cervical or extracapsular or extra-capsular or trochant* or subtrochant* or pertrochant* or intertrochant*) N5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)) OR AB ((hip OR hips OR cervical or femoral* OR femur* or intracapsular or intra-capsular or subcapital or sub-capital or transcervical or trans-cervical or basicervical or basi-cervical or extracapsular or extra-capsular or trochant* or subtrochant* or pertrochant* or intertrochant*) N5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)) OR SU ((hip OR hips OR cervical or femoral* OR femur* or intracapsular or intra-capsular or subcapital or sub-capital or transcervical or trans-cervical or basicervical or basi-cervical or extracapsular or extra-capsular or trochant* or subtrochant* or pertrochant* or intertrochant*) N5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*))
- S3 (TI (((head OR neck OR proximal) N5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)) AND (femoral OR femur*))) OR (AB (((head OR neck OR proximal) N5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)) AND (femoral OR femur*)) OR (SU (((head OR neck OR proximal) N5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)) AND (femoral OR femur*))
- S4 S1 OR S2 OR S3
- S5 TI (('clinical prediction' OR "clinical score*" OR "decision rule*" OR 'diagnostic accuracy' OR "diagnostic rule*" OR 'diagnostic score*' OR 'diagnostic value' OR 'predictive outcome*' OR 'predictive rule*' OR 'predictive score*' OR 'predictive value' OR "predictive risk*" OR "prediction outcome*" OR "prediction rule*" OR "prediction score*" OR "prediction value*" OR "prediction risk*" OR "risk score*" OR "risk model": OR "risk adjust*" OR "risk prediction" OR "validation decision*" OR "validation rule*" OR "validation score*" OR (derivation AND validation) OR (derived AND validated) OR (sensitivity AND specificity))) OR AB (('clinical prediction' OR "clinical score*" OR "decision rule*" OR 'diagnostic accuracy' OR "diagnostic rule*" OR 'diagnostic score*' OR 'diagnostic value' OR 'predictive outcome*' OR 'predictive rule*' OR 'predictive score*' OR 'predictive value' OR "predictive risk*" OR "prediction outcome*" OR "prediction rule*" OR "prediction score*" OR "prediction value*" OR "prediction risk*" OR "risk score*" OR "risk model": OR "risk adjust*" OR "risk prediction" OR "validation decision*" OR "validation rule*" OR "validation score*" OR (derivation AND validation) OR (derived AND validated) OR (sensitivity AND specificity))) OR SU (('clinical prediction' OR "clinical score*" OR "decision rule*" OR 'diagnostic accuracy' OR "diagnostic rule*" OR 'diagnostic score*' OR 'diagnostic value' OR 'predictive outcome*' OR 'predictive rule*' OR 'predictive score*' OR 'predictive value' OR "predictive risk*" OR "prediction outcome*" OR "prediction rule*" OR "prediction score*" OR "prediction value*" OR "prediction risk*" OR "risk score*" OR "risk model": OR "risk adjust*" OR "risk prediction" OR "validation decision*" OR "validation rule*" OR "validation score*" OR (derivation AND validation) OR (derived AND validated) OR (sensitivity AND specificity)))
- S6 TI ("Stratification" or "Discrimination" or "Discriminate" or "c-statistic" or "c statistic" or "Area under the curve" or "Calibration" or "Indices" or "Algorithm") OR AB ("Stratification" or "Discrimination" or "Discriminate" or "c-statistic" or "c statistic" or "Area under the curve" or "Calibration" or "Indices" or "Algorithm") OR SU ("Stratification" or "Discrimination" or "Discriminate" or "c-statistic" or "c statistic" or "Area under the curve" or "Calibration" or "Indices" or "Algorithm")
- S7 (MH "ROC Curve")
- S8 S5 OR S6 OR S7
- S9 S4 AND S8
- S10 "Hip Fracture Score"
- S11 S9 OR S10

- S12 TI (Mortality OR death OR died OR survival OR readmi* OR re-admi* OR rehospitali* OR re-hospitali* OR re-operat* OR reoperat* OR failure OR revision OR periprosthe* OR peri-prosthe* OR peri-implant OR osteonecro* OR "avascular necro*" OR non-union OR "non union" OR extrusion OR cutout OR cut-out OR re-fracture OR refracture OR "second fracture" OR recurrent OR subsequent OR dislocation OR infect* OR complicat* OR adverse or event* OR reaction OR transfusion OR thrombo* OR embol* OR residen* OR living OR home OR location OR lived OR function* OR adhere* OR medicat* OR persist* OR pain* OR mobil* OR walk* OR ambulat* OR quality OR QOL OR activit*) OR AB (Mortality OR death OR died OR survival OR readmi* OR re-admi* OR rehospitali* OR re-hospitali* OR re-operat* OR reoperat* OR failure OR revision OR periprosthe* OR peri-prosthe* OR peri-implant OR osteonecro* OR "avascular necro*" OR non-union OR "non union" OR extrusion OR cutout OR cut-out OR re-fracture OR refracture OR "second fracture" OR recurrent OR subsequent OR dislocation OR infect* OR complicat* OR adverse or event* OR reaction OR transfusion OR thrombo* OR embol* OR residen* OR living OR home OR location OR lived OR function* OR adhere* OR medicat* OR persist* OR pain* OR mobil* OR walk* OR ambulat* OR quality OR QOL OR activit*) OR SU (Mortality OR death OR died OR survival OR readmi* OR re-admi* OR rehospitali* OR re-hospitali* OR re-operat* OR reoperat* OR failure OR revision OR periprosthe* OR peri-prosthe* OR peri-implant OR osteonecro* OR "avascular necro*" OR non-union OR "non union" OR extrusion OR cutout OR cut-out OR re-fracture OR refracture OR "second fracture" OR recurrent OR subsequent OR dislocation OR infect* OR complicat* OR adverse or event* OR reaction OR transfusion OR thrombo* OR embol* OR residen* OR living OR home OR location OR lived OR function* OR adhere* OR medicat* OR persist* OR pain* OR mobil* OR walk* OR ambulat* OR quality OR QOL OR activit*)
- S13 S11 AND S12

Scopus

(((TITLE-ABS-KEY (hip OR hips OR cervical OR femoral* OR femur* OR intracapsular OR "intra capsular" OR subcapital OR "sub capital" OR transcervical OR "trans cervical" OR basicervical OR "basi cervical" OR extracapsular OR "extra capsular" OR trochant* OR subtrochant* OR petrochant* OR intertrochant*) W/5 fracture*) OR (TITLE-ABS-KEY ((head OR neck OR proximal) W/5 (fracture* OR break* OR broke*)) AND (femoral OR femur*))) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY ('clinical AND prediction' OR "clinical score*" OR "decision rule*" OR 'diagnostic AND accuracy' OR "diagnostic rule*" OR 'diagnostic AND score*' OR 'diagnostic AND value' OR 'predictive AND outcome*' OR 'predictive AND rule*' OR 'predictive AND score*' OR 'predictive AND value' OR "predictive risk*" OR "prediction outcome*" OR "prediction rule*" OR "prediction score*" OR "prediction value*" OR "prediction risk*" OR "risk score*" OR "risk model" : OR "risk adjust*" OR "risk prediction" OR "validation decision*" OR "validation rule*" OR "validation score*" OR (derivation AND validation) OR (derived AND validated) OR (sensitivity AND specificity) OR "Stratification" OR "Discrimination" OR "Discriminate" OR "c-statistic" OR "c statistic" OR "Area under the curve" OR "Calibration" OR "Indices" OR "Algorithm" OR "ROC Curve" OR "Hip Fracture Score")) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (Mortality OR death OR died OR survival OR readmi* OR re-admi* OR rehospitali* OR re-hospitali* OR re-operat* OR reoperat* OR failure OR revision OR periprosthe* OR peri-prosthe* OR peri-implant OR osteonecro* OR "avascular necro*" OR non-union OR "non union" OR extrusion OR cutout OR cut-out OR re-fracture OR refracture OR "second fracture" OR recurrent OR subsequent OR dislocation OR infect* OR complicat* OR adverse or event* OR reaction OR transfusion OR thrombo* OR embol* OR residen* OR living OR home OR location OR lived OR function* OR adhere* OR medicat* OR persist* OR pain* OR mobil* OR walk* OR ambulat* OR quality OR QOL OR activit*)